

Relevance and Need for a Uniform Civil Code in India

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Abstract

Uniform Civil Code is observed as the same set of secular civil laws so as to govern all people irrespective of their religion, caste and tribe. The need for such a code was felt to take into account the constitutional mandate of securing justice and equality for all its citizens. In simple words, Uniform Civil Code was defined as a proposal in which the personal laws of the country should be replaced on the basis of the scriptures and customs of each major religious community in India with a common set governing every citizen. The personal laws vary widely on the basis of their sources, philosophy and application. Therefore, an inherent difficulty and resistance is seen so as to bringing people together and to unite them when they are governed by different religions and personal laws. It is often seen that Communalism breeds discrimination at two levels:• Between people of different religions and Between the two sexes. It was only the Hindu law where its codification was taken forward that too in spite of great protest but till now codification of Muslim law is still a sensitized issue owing to its polarization.

Keywords: Indian Law & Uniform Civil Code.

Introduction

Uniform Civil Code means a set of common Civil Laws or personal laws for every citizen of India irrespective of any religion. Uniform Civil Code is observed as the same set of secular civil laws so as to govern all people irrespective of their religion, caste and tribe. The need for such a code was felt to take into account the constitutional mandate of securing justice and equality for all its citizens. In simple words, Uniform Civil Code was defined as a proposal in which the personal laws of the country should be replaced on the basis of the scriptures and customs of each major religious community in India with a common set governing every citizen. After being applicable to all, such a code becomes futile pertaining to our personal laws whether it is Hindu law, Muslim law or any other personal law in which the issues related to marriage, divorce, succession, inheritance, adoption and other family matters. There is multiplicity of family laws in India and they have their own personal laws like the Hindus have their Hindu law (Hindu Marriage Act, 1955), Muslims have their Muslim law, Christians have their Christians Marriage Act, 1872, the Indian Divorce Act, 1869, the Jews have their unmodified customary marriage law, Parsis have their own Parsi marriage and Divorce Act, 1936 and other laws. It is seen personally so far that each person carries his own law wherever he goes in India. The personal laws vary widely on the basis of their sources, philosophy and application. Therefore, an inherent difficulty and resistance is seen so as to bringing people together and to unite them when they are governed by different religions and personal laws.

The debates regarding the establishment of a uniform system of personal laws in India dates back to the times of the British Raj in India. Prior to the colonial period, the state kept its hands off the personal laws of its subjects. This was done to ensure peace and tranquility amongst the diverse sections of the Indian society and the consequent ease of ruling over them.

Initially, the Warren Hastings Plan of 1772 provided that the Hindus and Muslims were to take recourse of their respective personal laws in disputes related to inheritance, marriage, etc. The British, after consolidating their administrative position in India, changed the entire criminal law system and brought about the Indian Penal Code of 1860 which was aimed to be made uniformly applicable in India. Various matters of civil law were also brought under the British system of ruling. Although this resulted in the modification and interpretation of personal laws by the foreign British judges who had negligible ideas about the Indian scenario, the complete unification of civil laws related to family wasn't done.

According to article 25 and 26 of the Indian Constitution people are entitled to freedom of religion and freedom to manage religious affairs. They come under fundamental rights. UCC will be a new law instead of mixed personal laws so that the chances of giving privilege to specific one does not increase and one of the main reasons of UCC is to prevent biases. It would not ask a Muslim to perform Hindu rituals and vice versa instead it shall regulate marriage, adoption and succession without any gender discrimination.

The personal laws are taken from the customs which were favourable to the men society. The reason behind the arrival of Hindu and Muslim personal laws in the early 20th century was to protect the private realm of the family and keep away from the eyes of the colonial state. The men are always considered superior in personal matters such as marriage, adoption, maintenance or even the succession. Women are discriminated in every aspect of life. Before 1955 polygamy which is a custom of having more than one wife at the same time was common among the Hindus. Even when polygamy was abolished from Hindu Personal Law there was an aggressive reaction by Hindu men who threatened to convert into Islam as they felt that they were being deprived of their customary rights. According to the Hindu Succession Act 1956, the rights of inheritance in ancestral property were not given to daughters. At present all the Hindus have also different Hindu Personal Law based on the states of India, like a person who belongs to Sikh religion is allowed to carry a dagger known as kripa but at the same time if others carry it they will be arrested by the police. In the case of adoption a Hindu women is not allowed to adopt a child and for that matter she cannot even become natural guardian of her own child till the lifetime of her husband. In the case of Muslim society it is equally harsh and discriminating against women. From the beginning itself the women are given secondary status. In Islamic religion, husband is allowed to marry and have more than one wife but the same rule does not apply to the wife. There are several laws which infringe women's right and one of them is "Triple Talaq." According to Triple Talaq a Muslim man can give divorce to his wife by saying Talaq thrice and wife cannot do anything about it. India is filled with cases where husband have divorced their wives over phone calls, messages etc. Under Muslim Personal Law a Muslim man is liable to give maintenance only till the period of Iddat and not beyond it. Bases on the above personal laws a demand for the implementation of UCC in India raised by the people and especially women all over the country. They felt the need of Uniform Civil Code to fill the gap of equality. The dissatisfaction and feeling of letdown was conveyed by the All India Women's Conference (AIWC) with male dominated legislature.

The Goa is the only state in India where UCC exists for all the communities irrespective of gender, religion and caste. This code was framed in 19th and 20th century by the Portuguese colonist. The state has a common family law. All the people whether belong to Hindu, Muslim, Christians follow same rule related to divorce, marriage and succession. No doubt why Goa is on its way to become a highly developed and progressive state. In Goa there is equal distribution of property between husband and wife and also between children irrespective of gender. All the Muslims who married and registered it in Goa cannot exercise polygamy and Triple Talaq. After Divorce the property will be divided equally between husband and wife. The registration of marriage is compulsory in Goa. When Goa released from slavery, government removed all the laws made by the colonist except Family law as all the communities in Goa wanted it.

Role of Indian Judiciary:

The judiciary has faced a plethora of problems in upholding the social reforms in the private sphere that the legislation tries to bring through various enactments. There is a surfeit of cases that takes into consideration the concept of Uniform Civil Code. Some of them are as follows: Mohd. Ahmed Khan v. Shah Bano (referred to as Shah Bano case) in which a divorced Muslim woman was brought within the ambit of Section 125 of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 by the Supreme Court in which it was declared by the Apex court that she was entitled for maintenance even after the completion of iddat period.

S.R.Bomma v. Union of India, it was held by the court that religion is the matter of individual faith and cannot be mixed with the secular activities. Secular activities can be regulated by the State by enacting a law.

Sarla Mudgal v. Union of India, in which Justice Kuldip Singh reiterated the need for the Parliament to frame a Uniform Civil Code, which would help the cause of national integration by removing contradictions based on ideologies. Therefore, the responsibility entrusted on the State under Article 44 of the Constitution whereby a Uniform Civil Code must be secured has been urged by the Supreme Court repeatedly as a matter of urgency.

Mary Roy v. State of Kerela, where it was argued before the Supreme Court was that certain provisions of Travancore Christian Succession Act, 1916, were unconstitutional under Art. 14 Under these provisions, on the death of an intestate, his widow was entitled to have only a life interest terminable at her death or remarriage

and his daughter. It was also argued that the Travancore Act had been superseded by the Indian Succession Act, 1925. The Supreme Court avoided examining the question whether gender inequality in matters of succession and inheritance violated Art.14, but, nevertheless, ruled that the Travancore Act had been superseded by the Indian Succession Act. Mary Roy has been characterized as a “momentous” decision in the direction of ensuring gender equality in the matter of succession.

Bai Tahira v. Ali Hussain Fisaalli, according to the Ambedkarian point of view, he states that: “Speaking for myself, there are several excellent provisions of the Muslim law understood in its pristine and progressive intendment which may adorn India’s common civil code. There is more in Mohammed than in Manu, if interpreted in its humanist liberalism and away from the desert context, which helps women and orphans, modernises marriage and morals, widens divorce and inheritance.”

State of Bombay v. Narasu Appa Mali, in this case the constitutional validity of the Bombay (Prevention of Hindu Bigamous Marriages) Act, 1946 was to be determined by the High Court of Bombay. One of the two major contentions was that it was violative of articles 14 and 15 since the Hindus were singled out to abolish bigamy while the Muslim counterparts remained at full liberty to contract more than one marriage and this was discrimination on the grounds of religion. Questions such as these were raised due to an absence of a common civil code and clash of different principles in different personal laws.

Srinivasa Aiyar v. Saraswati Ammal, in this case the High Court of Madras upheld the validity of Madras Prohibition of Bigamy Act on similar grounds.

The whole debate can be summed up by the judgment given by Justice R.M. Sahai. He said: Ours is a secular democratic republic. Freedom of religion is the core of our culture. Even the slightest of deviation shakes the social fiber. But religious practices, vocative of human rights and dignity and sacerdotal suffocation of essentially civil and material freedom are not autonomy but oppression. Therefore, a unified code is imperative, both for protection of the oppressed and for promotion of national unity and solidarity.

Conclusion

The Indian independence from the British Raj in 1947 led to intense debates on the application of a Uniform Civil Code for regulating the matters related to personal laws in the Indian community. The concept of equality provided in the Constitution of India and the Preamble therein and the unequal personal laws of the Indian communities contradicted vehemently with each other. To resolve the same, the makers of the Indian Constitution struck up an intricate compromise which was to mention the concept of Uniform Civil Code in the Directive Principles of State Policy as Article 44.

Article 44 of the Indian Constitution (Directive Principles of the State Policy) states that “The state shall endeavour to secure for its citizens a uniform civil code throughout the territory of India.” This article has always been a subject of debate and such debate has also left the subject of this article i.e. uniform civil code staggering and whirling in an orbit on an axis on its own with the rotating public opinion. The Constitution of India enshrines Article 44 of the DPSP with a view to achieve the uniformity of law, its secularization in order to make it equitable and non-discriminatory. The preamble of the Indian Constitution which constitutes a Secular Democratic Republic’ which implies that there shall be no state religion and no state shall discriminate on the basis of religion. The uniform civil code must strike a balance between the protection of fundamental rights and religious principles of different communities of personal laws of each religion that comprises of separate ingredients and are founded on different ideologies. It is often seen that Communalism breeds discrimination at two levels: Between people of different religions and Between the two sexes. It was only the Hindu law where its codification was taken forward that too in spite of great protest but till now codification of Muslim law is still a sensitized issue owing to its polarization.

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